

Discussion to accompany CGI Simple Lithology vocabulary

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Introduction

Science vocabularies have been constructed to provide geologic data to users in government, business, and academia a consistent terminology of categories for concepts and property values. The use of a clearly defined vocabulary, with definitions developed to avoid ambiguity in the use of terms, is essential for consistent communication of science concepts to a wide variety of data users who have vastly different levels of familiarity with geologic terms and concepts. Implementation of any geoscience information system requires a collection of science terms and definitions to populate descriptions of rocks, geologic units, and structures (Giles and others, 1997).

This term list is a concept vocabulary. The identity of a controlled concept (represented by a term from the vocabulary) is based on its definition, not the actual word used. The preferred name or term associated with the concept in the vocabulary is a label for the concept used in human communication, which corresponds a region of some particular concept space (see Gardenfors, 2000). The point of this vocabulary is to define the concept spaces and categories to hierarchically partition each space in a useful manner consistent with standard geoscience usage. The names given to the categories attempt to match common usage to the extent possible, but because natural language is not constructed as a coherent logical system, there are discrepancies between the defined categories and some familiar usages; this is necessary for coherence. In the end, the name given to the category is not the issue; the important science question is whether the category is a useful subdivision of the natural world, and if it is clearly enough defined to distinguish from other categories.

This vocabulary is the outgrowth of several years of compilation and testing, first in the arena of the North America Geologic Map Data Model science language technical team efforts (North American Geologic Map Data Model Steering Committee Science Language Technical Team (SLTT), 2004), and then in the course developing and testing database implementation for the NGMDB project, and in an international working group extending these efforts to develop standards for international information interchange (<https://www.seegrid.csiro.au/twiki/bin/view/CGIModel/ConceptDefinitionsTG>). This work evolved from attempts at rather exhaustive categorization schemes with more than a thousand terms. This large vocabulary resulted from an attempt to account for all the composite lithology concepts that have a texture/fabric and a composition/mineralogy or other property dimensions. This vocabulary represents an effort to develop a list of on the order of 100-200 terms that would be more manageable for users.

The categories defined in this document are designed for populating GeoSciML interchange documents, and some familiarity with the GeoSciML data model will be helpful to understand the material presented here. The GeoSciML schema allows multiple lithology categories to be assigned. This logical conjunction (combination) of categories is an essential part of keeping the number of lithologic categories manageable. The ability to combine concepts in categorizing a rock type is particularly significant with sedimentary and metamorphic rocks, where texture/fabric and composition/petrographic criteria are typically combined to define a category.

Usage notes

Hierarchy

The spreadsheet or text-based display of the vocabulary using the single tree-hierarchy encoding a single category for each category is somewhat misleading, because the concepts in the lithology vocabulary are inherently polyhierarchical. A single, tree-hierarchical listing forces arbitrary choices of which possible parent to show, and which properties to use first for branching the hierarchy display.

The lithology concept space is quite complex, with numerous property dimensions. Many terms are defined using only a subset of the properties in the concept space for a subsuming broader category. Commonly the subcategory distinctions are based on properties that are not normative for the subsuming broader category. For instance, clastic sedimentary rock has sub-categories sandstone and diamictite. Clastic sedimentary rock is defined based on consolidation and genesis (sedimentary, and clastic). The sandstone subcategory is differentiated based on grain size, while the diamictite category is differentiated based on sorting. It is possible for a rock to meet both the definition of sandstone and the definition of diamictite. On the other hand, carbonate sediment is defined based on consolidation, genesis, and mineralogic composition. It has one set of subcategories based on grain size (e.g. carbonate sand), and another set based on mineralogical composition (calcareous carbonate sediment). The mineralogical composition subcategories define more specific subdivisions of the composition property within the range that defines the broader category.

In general, how should users choose among alternate permissible classifications? The philosophy of the system is to define named lithologic categories using independent (to the degree possible) concept dimensions (e.g. grain size and mineralogy). These categories are meant to be combined to define the composite categories that are typically used to classify rocks. Ideally, the information system in which the terminology is used should allow multiple categories to be assigned to characterize a particular rock type. Failing this, there are two choices: 1) create a user defined vocabulary that combines the CGI simple lithology concepts as necessary for the users geologic setting; 2) choose one of several possible ‘facets’ to categorize the rocks using some sort of consistent criteria within the scope of the dataset being built. The first case is preferable because there will be no loss of information when generating interchange documents using GeoSciML; the mapping between user terms and CGI SimpleLithology can be used to insert all the appropriate categories in the compositionPart elements in the interchange document.

In summary, it is important to bear in mind that the hierarchical relationships mean ‘IsA’, as in any sandstone ‘IsA’ clastic sedimentary rock. The direct subcategories of a given category (like clastic sedimentary rock) may be overlapping. Overlapping subcategories of a given category may often be grouped into non-overlapping subsets that represent variation along some particular property dimension. The properties that differentiate such groups of non-overlapping categories are ideally independent, but in the real world there may be some dependency. For example Schist (as defined here) means a rocks consisting of aligned tabular or acicular mineral grains. In practice, these will almost always be mica or amphibole minerals, so there is a significant correlation between mineralogy composition and fabric in this case. The system is meant to be constructed such that where such correlations exist, they are not necessary condition (e.g. in the example above, mica-rich composition does not necessarily mean the rock is schist).

Sandstone composed of carbonate particles; clastic and siliciclastic

The distinction of a carbonate grainstone (in the Carbonate sedimentary rock) part of the system from a carbonate lithic arenite (a Clastic sedimentary rock) is based on distinction of the kind of particles (sand grains) forming the rock, specifically based on interpretation of their origin. A carbonate grainstone is composed of ‘intraclasts’ in the terminology of Folk (19...), that is clasts formed by processes within a basin of deposition; typically these are largely skeletal parts from organisms like crinoids or bivalves, also including pellets, ooids, and various other types. A carbonate lithic arenite is a sandstone composed of carbonate fragments eroded from previously lithified carbonate rock and transported by wind, moving water, or sediment gravity flow processes into the basin of deposition. This distinction requires that primary sedimentary textures are well preserved, and in an altered rock the distinction may become difficult or impossible. If the context of the rock is known, this can often be used to infer whether it is a grainstone or sandstone, but lacking that, it would have to be classified as a carbonate sedimentary rock if it was still determined to be sedimentary, or marble if the alteration is extensive enough to make it a metamorphic rock.

It has also been suggested that the term ‘siliclastic’ is more appropriate than ‘clastic’ for the various clastic sedimentary material categories. This point was discussed extensively in SLTTs (2004), which recommended the use of ‘terrigenous clastic’. The CGI committee’s review of the terminology determined that ‘terrigenous clastic’ is redundant, and logically equivalent to ‘clastic. The term ‘siliciclastic’ was rejected because the category is explicitly genetic, not compositional as would be denoted by use of ‘siliciclastic’.

Number of igneous, sedimentary, and metamorphic categories

“The metamorphic rocks section is weak. Igneous rocks seem to be over-represented: 49 kinds, versus 16 varieties of metamorphic rock and 24 varieties of sedimentary rock.” Any specialist could make the same argument about the rocks they know best. Note that the igneous category includes 3 very different groups of rocks—volcanic, pyroclastic, and intrusive (phaneritic); these should probably be treated at the same rank as metamorphic and sedimentary. This vocabulary will evolve over time, and the division of categories in various rock domains will change based on scientific development and better understanding of what is useful for information interchange. More than likely several alternate vocabularies will evolve designed for specific communities; interoperability will depend on mapping between these vocabularies.

‘Material’ categories

The reasoning for the presence of the “material” categories needs to be explained. These are included as a short cut to enable queries like ‘find all units that contain igneous rocks’ or ‘find all units that contain non consolidated material.’ In the GeoSciML data model, the distinction of igneous, sedimentary, composite genesis materials could be made if `GeologicUnit.compositionPart.Rock.preferredAge.Event.eventProcess` properties are specified and can be hierarchically analyzed. A similarly complex query path would need to be utilized to distinguish the other material categories. Including the generic ‘material’ classes, which are distinguished based on the basic genetic or composition categories--igneous, sedimentary, composite genesis, clastic, carbonate etc. -- enables the queries with a simple data model. It remains to be seen in practice what the best trade off is between adding terms and complexity to the lithology vocabulary to simplify queries, versus keeping the vocabulary simple but requiring more complex query construction and processing.

Phaneritic vs Aphanitic

Quote from SLTTm (2004): “The IUGS Subcommittee on the Systematics of Metamorphic Rocks (SCMR) extended the use of igneous grain-size terms ‘phaneritic’ (large enough to be distinguished by the unaided eye) and ‘aphanitic’ (too fine grained to be distinguished by the unaided eye) to metamorphic rocks, noting that these qualitative definitions correspond approximately to “aphanitic” (ca. <0.1 mm) and “phaneritic” (ca. >0.1 mm) (Schmid and others, 2002, Table 5). The British Geological Survey rock classification (Gillespie and Styles, 1999, section 3.2, p. 6) applies “phaneritic” and “aphanitic” to metamorphic rocks but interprets the actual grain sizes differently:

“Placing the boundary between ‘medium grained’ and ‘fine grained’ crystals in crystalline igneous and metamorphic rocks at 0.25 mm essentially divides aphanitic rocks (in which individual crystals are too fine grained to be distinguished by the naked eye) from phaneritic rocks (in which individual crystals can be distinguished by the naked eye)... This is also the boundary between medium and fine sand for sedimentary clasts.”

Others interpret the phaneritic-aphanitic (visible-invisible) distinction as approximately equivalent to the sand-silt grain size distinction for sediments, which is variously considered to be in the range of 0.032 mm (Robertson, 1999, BGS grain size scheme) to 0.062 mm (Jackson, 1997) to 0.074 mm (Engineering grain-size scale, ASTM standard D422-63; D643-78). This is smaller than the phaneritic-aphanitic boundary of 0.1 mm proposed by Schmid and others (2002). However, in practical terms, such detailed grain size distinctions are impossible in the field, and very difficult under any conditions. The IUGS usage is endorsed and applied in this classification.”

High precision grain size distinction for lithified material in this size range (close to the thickness of a thin section) is somewhat specious, particularly if the material has undergone diagenesis or alteration, which is commonly the case. The BGS is revising their rock-naming scheme, changing from 0.032 mm to 0.064 mm the common boundary that separates mud-grade and sand-grade fragments, fine-ash-grade and coarse-ash-grade fragments, and very-fine-crystalline and fine-crystalline materials (M. Gillespie, personal communication, 2009). For practical purposes in lithified rock, it is suggested that 0.064 and 0.1 mm are indistinguishably different; either will do (check what published IUGS meta rock book uses...).

Glassy, fragmental, crystalline

“Your scheme uses the term ‘Glassy igneous rock’ for rocks with >90% glass, but the same term is approved by both the IUGS scheme and the RCS for rocks with 50-80% glass; it will be unfortunate if the same term is used with significantly different meaning in separate schemes.” What happens if there is more than 80% glass? We didn’t want to go into the whole project of trying to systematize obsidian, pitchstone, etc. Our glassy rock concept obviously corresponds to these categories. There is an inconstancy in the systems here. Perhaps Gillespie and Styles usage of glassy (50-100% glass) makes most sense, given that GeoSciML allows representation of conjunctions (Glassy igneous rock and porphyry and rhyolitic rock). For CGI purposes need a name for category of rocks with >80% glass? Also need to review how glass is accounted for in modal mineral composition description.

Pyroclastic rocks may be composed of glass, as in the pyroclastic fragments are composed of glass, lava breccia may like wise be composed of glass. As usual, the first level distinction is between crystalline and fragmental. Intrusive breccia is especially problematic in that it is both crystalline and fragmental.

Specific lithology category questions:

What about mantle tectonites (metamorphic rocks with peridotite mineralogy)? Given the current vocabulary, such rocks would have to be identified as gneiss or ‘mylonitic rock’, composition category ‘ultramafic’, deformation environment ‘mantle’. This is an example of the trade off between expanding the vocabulary or requiring data providers to expose more complex data content (and data consumers to construct more complex queries). The point of the ‘simple vocabulary’ is to keep common things simple, which thus requires judgments about what is ‘common.’ It is useful to consider the lithology category vocabulary as a collection of key words to help people zero in on the kinds of rocks that interest them.

Cataclasite. The perplexing question is the nature of the cohesive cataclasite category. Is it real? Can it be distinguished from mylonite? These rocks are distinguished from mylonite by the absence of plastically deformed mineral grains, i.e. mineral grains that have obviously changed shape relative to their protolith without fracturing visible by the unaided eye. Operational criteria is the nature of the particles in the rock, which in cataclasite appear to be predominantly broken pieces of once larger particles have been fractured, or multi-grain fragments in which fractures have developed across pre-existing grain boundaries, and in which relict texture from the protolith is preserved. Distinction from indurated varieties of the breccia-gouge series is also difficult, and hinges on interpretation of the nature of the matrix. In indurated breccia-gouge series rocks, the matrix is interpreted as secondary cement that bonds an aggregate of particles that were in frictional contact but not bound materially during deformation. In cataclasite, the observed matrix is interpreted to be representative of the material as it was during deformation, which occurred by a poorly understood collection of grain boundary sliding and fracture processes.

Mylonite. “Most mylonites I have seen don’t have anastomosing foliation or S-C fabrics; these are typically present in rocks that have a very low volume of fine-grained matrix. ‘Tectonic grain-size reduction’ is a pretty fuzzy—useless?--notion.” The following quote from SLTTm (2004) explains the thinking for mylonitic rocks:

“Deformation in faults and shear zones occurs in a continuum of environmental conditions from near the Earth’s surface, where discontinuous/brittle processes dominate, to high temperature conditions deep in the Earth where continuous deformation and crystal-plastic processes dominate (Sibson, 1977; Passchier and Trouw, 1996). Foliated, deformed rocks formed in the crystal-plastic regime are included in the mylonite-series. Mylonite-series rocks are commonly lineated. They typically contain fabric elements such as quartz ribbons, mica fish, asymmetric porphyroclasts, S-C composite planar fabrics, and microstructures indicative of crystal-plastic deformation (e.g. recovery and recrystallization, see Sibson, 1977; Passchier and Trouw, 1996; Snoke and Tullis, 1998). The matrix consists of new or recrystallized mineral grains that are interpreted to be smaller than the mineral grains in the original, undeformed protolith. In cases where the protolith was very fine-grained or is unknown, problems in applying this definition may be overcome to some extent by observing the progressive development of fabric and grain-size reduction along the margins of high-strain zones. The distinction between relatively high-temperature cataclastic rocks and mylonite-series rocks is based on the presence of a foliation produced by aligned mineral grains whose shape has been modified by crystal-plastic deformation in mylonite-series rocks. Standard classification schemes for mylonite-series rocks are based on the degree of deformation-related grain-size reduction, which is quantified as the percentage of matrix produced by tectonic reduction in grain size (Sibson, 1977; Wise and others, 1984; Scholz, 1990; Passchier and Trouw, 1996; Snoke and Tullis, 1998). Snoke and Tullis (1998, Table 0.1) endorsed Scholz’s (1990, Table 3.1) slightly modified version of Sibson’s (1977) classification of fault rocks. We adopt that classification here with minor modifications for database applications.”

The only thing to say is that the concept of tectonic reduction in grain size is pretty well embedded in the literature about this sort of rock, and works for some people. Stay tuned for a new classification system as we learn more about how rocks deform, and how that deformation is recorded in the rocks.

Organic sedimentary material. As organic material is commonly not mineral, Organic sedimentary material categories should be subcategories of “biogenic sediment.” The material that composes particles in the organic-rich sedimentary rocks is indeed different from the mineral materials that compose most rocks. NADM C1 (2004) places these in subcategory of EarthMaterial named ‘OrganicMaterial’ for this reason. The organic category is defined based on the composition, and the biogenic category is defined based on the origin/genesis of the material. Inclusion in the organic material category implies biogenic origin, but not vice versa. Much biogenic material is skeletal fragment that have standard mineral compositions (aragonite, calcite, apatite...). This conceptual framework is inherited from the SLTTs (2004) schemes, and from the Hallsworth and Knox (1999) scheme.

Lahar deposits. This brings up the distinction between Earth material (as defined by NADM C1, 2004) and ‘deposits’. Deposits are composed of Earth material. A deposit is an assemblage of Earth material and geologic structure (again in the broad, NADM C1 sense), these are typically sedimentary structures, and the term is typically used in connection with sedimentary (or pyroclastic) accumulations. Deposit nomenclature almost always carries genetic connotations or denotations. Some other examples include turbidite, olistostrome, point bar sequence, deltaic deposit. The concept can be extended to include some other complex assemblages of rocks that are commonly treated as entities—ophiolite, melange, chaos deposits. In the case of a lahar, the actual material category from the SimpleLithology vocabulary would most likely be ‘diamicton’ or ‘diamictite’; to fully describe a lahar deposit, one would have to add that its depositional process is ‘mass-wasting’, perhaps ‘pyroclastic’ depending on your interpretation of the lahar, and setting is something like ‘stratovolcano’.

Gneiss vs Schist. “A gneiss with a plagioclase grain-shape fabric (rotation of phenocrysts without recrystallization) has schistosity. This is wrong.” The distinction of gneiss and schist is as tricky as any that geologists make, and the variety of definitions speaks to the lack of any kind of ‘natural’ categories here (see review in SLTTm, 2004). Is a schistosity defined by thin tabular plagioclase any more ‘wrong’ than schistosity defined by glaucophane in a ‘blueschist’ or actinolite in a ‘greeschist’ or hornblende in a ‘hornblende schist?’ The CGI simple lithology scheme rejected the IUGS approach of defining a schist based on the thickness of tabular plates that the rock can be split into because the criteria depends operationally on the degree of weathering, and would seem to require a planar (not folded or crenulated) character to the foliation. Use of mineralogical criteria to define schist is incompatible with its framing as a texture/fabric related category, and also becomes problematic when schistose fabric is observed in unexpected settings, for example a specularite (hematite) schist.

Non-clastic siliceous sedimentary rock with subcategory Biogenic silica sedimentary rock: why is this distinction needed? There are varieties of non clastic silica of uncertain or non biogenic origin. The most common are probably Proterozoic siliceous exhalite deposits commonly associated with iron formations. There is some difference of opinion as well as to the biogenic versus chemogenic origin of many more recent marine cherts. Inclusion of the generic (non-clastic siliceous) category allows clear statement of when a deposit is known to be biogenic. The biogenic category would include rocks such as radiolarian chert and diatomite.

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